

BUREAUCRACY AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

A Case Study of Administrative Staff College of
NigeriaTopo- Badagry.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the research work was carried out by Ms Ilevbabor Geraldine Osenke (Student No. 04164213, under my supervision in the Department of Sociology, the University of Abuja.

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DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated first to God, in heaven, for his immeasurable grace.

To my parents, Mr Johnson & Mrs Veronica Ilevbabor, for their love, advice, financial and moral support.

And lastly, my siblings, Michael and Jerry Ilevbabor, whose support, care and general assistance have given me so much comfort, joy and a sense of stability.

Much Love.

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I would like to thank God Almighty, Professor W. Tile, the managing directors and the entire staff of the Administrative Staff College of Nigeria (ASCON) for their corporation.

I sincerely appreciate all my friends and acquaintances for their support, laughter and for providing a sense of mental, academic and social balance.

ABSTRACT

This work was embarked on to look into the notion of Bureaucracy and Organizational Effectiveness. According to Max Weber, in his ideal construct; bureaucracy was meant to increase speed, efficiency, effectiveness and precision. In a nutshell, bureaucracy is supposed to create rationality and speed in an organization. However, today, it is synonymous with red-tapism, inefficiency and ritualism of organization staff amongst other injustices and poor behaviours.

I intend to validate or invalidate this assertion on bureaucracy. As my empirical evidence in this pursuit, ASCON has been chosen as a case study. Having reviewed certain related literature, some tentative statements were made to be tested.

My findings revealed that bureaucratic principles play a role in informal groups in organizations. However, it has been observed that the existence of this form of association is inevitable because they contribute to an organizations effectiveness. The notion about the harms associated with bureaucratic principles was also validated.

Following this study on the reality of the organization, our knowledge of the organization has been further enhanced. Therefore, while not condemning bureaucratic features in their totality (as it causes no conscious effort to block organizational effectiveness), employees especially on the highest levels of an incumbent often encourage individual initiative and creativity, as they play a role towards organizational effectiveness.

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CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

Various forms of bureaucratic organizations have been established in human history for certain societal needs to be met. For example, the need for proper service delivery in Nigeria by the government, need for shelter, clothing and feeding. Men have, therefore, found out that they could not ignore one another and behave independently. This explains why we live in a world where bureaucratic organizations are increasingly becoming dominant forces.

Individuals spend a large percentage of their working lives in some form of bureaucracy or organization. They depend on them for their livelihood as well as for personal, professional and psychological satisfaction and development. A person quality of life is dependent on conditions within their jobs, the nature of their supervision, services delivered, the optics of policies and procedures that provide freedom of action. Lending credence to the pervasive influence of bureaucracy or organization on individuals in society Etzioni (1964) observed that our society is an “organizational society”- we are born in an organization and will most likely die in an organization.

The foregoing is to approximate that people are not independent units. In every society whether industrialized or non-industrialized, there are organizations in various forms, with wide ranges of organizational functions. The organization of a group consists of the development and maintenance of pattern activities that are aimed at the solution of many basic problems. For instance, the problem of distinctiveness, decision making, authority and so on.

It is pertinent to abandon the loose usage of the term bureaucracy for a more detailed analysis of the very bureaucratic organization of the study. The creation of Administrative Staff College of Nigeria (ASCON) spans from the year 1973 since its establishment by Decree 39 of 1973 now ASCON Act, Cap 6, Vol. 1 LFN 1990, has been very consistent in discharging its responsibilities as a major government training organization for both the Nigerian public and private economy. It has been able to work within the framework of its mandate in providing services in areas of

training, research and consultancy. It has become an outlet for the implementation of government reform initiatives- through assignment, engagement, consultancy and training.

Now that the present democratic leadership in the country is set to trend the path of changing its operating system to provide quality service, and make the citizens participants in the development process. ASCON has positively and swiftly identified and responded to the paradigm shift that is capable of ushering in service-oriented public administration, which emphasizes modernized and flexible public service normally regarded as the shopping floor for government activities and business.

The contents of the edition have incorporated all training requirements that will enhance performance, minimize widespread corruption and poverty which has already been an issue in the government quest to improve the lives of its citizens as a way of giving them the dividends of democracy.

In addition, the government has come up with a diagnostic concept of service delivery system, otherwise called SERVICOM as a reform initiative that calls for a “service compact with all Nigerians”, ASCON has buckled up to challenges of providing more essential services in the areas of training, research and consultancy, including other national assignments to complement the government effort to reduce the dominant role it has been playing as a major source of patronage rent-seeking. In this connection, ASCON services will help in training the capacity that will empower the private sector to become the engine for economic growth. We have equally been involved in human capital development in specific, World Bank Programmes, which included Health System Development Projects, HIV/Aids project and local Empowerment and Environmental Management Project (LEEMP). This momentum will be sustained in the next training session. The policy thrust of the college is to facilitate the process of re-engineering, re-positioning and restoration of economic prosperity through the promotion of good governance in tune with modified and rewarding capacity building.

In the light of the above, the dynamic approach to the Government Reforms Initiatives by ASCON, as reflected by its calendar of courses, is a new direction with customer satisfaction as a key factor in government business. It, therefore, follows with the service delivery as the “in-thing”

for vibrant economies in the world over, ASCON clients are assured of not only quality and improved serviced, but also getting services commensurate with the investment.

It is important to indicate that within the dispensation of the new world order of technology, ASCON has an array of programmes that will help the nation and indeed the West African sub-region in achieving higher productivity through Information and Communication Technology (ICT). It has restructured and redesigned its programmes to change the ways of doing things through its new approach to human and institutional capacity building and utilization to promote good governance. It, therefore, seizes this opportunity to implore our clients, customers, visitors and all those that patronize our services to feel at home, as it remains a bridge builder and a role model for other Management Development Institution (MDI's) in the whole of West African sub-region.

In it all, government departments are now committed to SERVICOM principles, namely;

AFFIRMATION, commitment to the service of the Nigerian nation.

CONVICTION, that Nigeria can only realize its full potential if citizens receive prompt and efficient services from the state.

CONSIDERATION, for the needs and rights of all Nigerians, to enjoy social and economic advancement.

DEDICATION, to deliver quality services to which all citizens are entitled in a timely, fair, honest, effective and transparent manner.

In it, the government gave several directives which included the setting up of ASCON to provide for the development of senior executives in all cadres in service delivery. Although ASCON was recommended to meet the Management Training needs of the public sector and to deliver quality services to which all citizens are entitled, the federal government considered it necessary to extend its coverage to the private sector.

The importance attached to training and learning comes out when it is further noted that the federal government spent 23,500 million on the construction of the first phase of ASCON. It must

be stressed at this point that ASCON was set up to meet the needs of training of staff abroad. Before now, in the absence of adequate local training facilities arrangements had to be made with some overseas bodies, for example, the Royal Institution of Public Administration in London, and the University of Pittsburgh in the United States of America. Overseas organizations with which no formal arrangement was made but to which officers were sent and still frequently being sent, include the Administrative Staff College, Henley-On-Thomas, and universities of the United Kingdom and the USA. These are costly, not only in terms of institutional charges and transportation but also of overseas allowances paid to officers on courses. The manpower requirements meant to be met are those on the high level, most especially senior executives in all cadres.

The need to refer to the prevailing point is to emphasize that it is a serious waste of scarce human and financial resources if trainees return.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Bureaucracy is not a modern invention. From history, we are told that as far back as 1650 BC, Chinese officials were chosen by examination. Merit ratings and writing reports in files were not uncommon. It has today penetrated all social institutions and deliberately structured them to meet the desired goals. Today the term bureaucracy in service delivery is synonymous with formal organizations.

Though designed to achieve rationality and order, bureaucracy does not entirely achieve the purpose. It is common knowledge that it notoriously slows to change innovation and reforms. Red tapeism and official rigidity are expressions that are commonly used to describe inefficiencies. But not just that, a great deal of scholars describes it as causing trained incapacities. That is a situation in which a worker can respond only in one way, regardless of what the conditions may be, simply because he is trained to carry out a specific in a particular way.

These two usages of the same term bureaucracy have forced our curiosity as to know why this has to be so, to understand why bureaucracy has been seen to lead to efficiency in its ideal nature and inefficiency in its 'real' nature, to determine the differences that exist and explanations that

could be adduced for these differences. The current debate notwithstanding bureaucracy remains the pervasive arrangement in modern human life and work, waxing stronger to achieving inefficiency in a bureaucratic organization.

In reaction to the above, attempts will be made to look at how the Administration Staff College of Nigeria (ASCON) has been faced with ineffectiveness as a result of strict devotion to rules and their structural nature. Also, attempts would be made to know the degree to which organizational members, not bureaucracy could inhibit the effectiveness of an organization. Furthermore, the impersonal nature of bureaucracy in the face of sentiments and emotions does not bring about organizational effectiveness.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

A great deal of scholars has criticized Max Weber's bureaucracy as well as other classical authorities who sought efficiency and effectiveness through tidy structuralization. Merton (1962) observed that the stress and strains in bureaucratic organizations has been deliberately ignored with undue emphasis on its merit. Blau (1956) criticized Weber for focusing exhaustively on the formal structure of bureaucracy. Blau holds the view that informal activities prohibited by organizational structure sometimes could lead to the attainment of organizational goals. The classical authorities contend that bureaucracy is essential to the operation of large scale industrial societies and as much it cannot be dispensed with. This statement has also been debunked by later scholars. To them, its efficiency has been overstressed and human relation and informal side of the enterprise may exert a stronger influence on behaviour than formal organizational provisions ignore (Bobbit, et al 1978).

With the above argument in mind, the purpose of this research work is therefore aimed at examining:

1. Some of the basic features of Weber's ideal bureaucratic type; and assert that it has positive consequences like nationality, speed, precision, continuity and negative consequence like rigidity, slowness to change, inefficiencies and kills innovative ideas.

2. The examination of the peculiar nature of the problems stated above in an organization- ASCON.
3. Proffer solutions and recommendations for the problems facing the smooth effectiveness of an organization to achieve a result-oriented organizational performance.

1.4 THE SCOPE/LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

Despite the use of scientific methods in social research, Sociologists have several limitations. The limitations in this research on ASCON emanates from the fact that Sociology cannot be a natural science but a social science dealing with humans and their society. In the study of the level of bureaucracy and organizational effectiveness in ASCON, there are a lot of limitations that occur as a result of the fact that social behaviour cannot be a regular behaviour, as people vary from individual to individual.

ASCON is made up of so many people with different behaviours, views, ideas, values, customs and more that would not necessarily be the same.

1.5 THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Bureaucracy and organizational effectiveness in ASCON is a modern invention, hence the introduction of new trends should be associated with the introduction of a new study on how to go about leading it to be more effective and efficient in all its bidding.

Understanding the fact that ASCON is a formal organization, one must out into consideration the need for bureaucratic capacitating activities and strict adherence to rules which govern the welfare of the organization.

Thus, the significance of this study is in an attempt to look at how ASCON (having been faced with ineffectiveness) can enhance its effectiveness and efficiency for the good of its staff and better service delivery to the larger public.

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

An attempt would be made to look at ASCONs ability for effectiveness to rules and its structural nature. And the understanding of the degree to which organizational members (and not bureaucratic members) can inhibit the effectiveness of an organization.

1.7 HYPOTHESES FORMULATION

Hypotheses are tentative statements identifying the relationship between variables. They are probability statements to be verified true or false. The purpose of any research enterprise, therefore, is to gather data to allow the researcher to either validate or invalidate the hypotheses.

Based on the nature of modern bureaucracies and their functional effectiveness as ASCON, the following Null hypotheses have been formulated to be tested by the study.

1. There is no relationship between strict adherence to bureaucratic rules and worker's initiative in ASCON, Lagos.
2. Bureaucracy is not related to organizational effectiveness in ASCON, Lagos.

1.8 DEFINITION OF MAJOR TERMS AND CONCEPTS USED IN THE STUDY

The terms considered necessary for clarification are bureaucracy, organizational, effectiveness, service, delivery, training recipient and learning:

- i. Bureaucracy: This concept has many definitions. The central theme is rationality. Its chief proponent did not give a specific definition but provided an ideal type by which analytical efforts can proceed. Depending on one's theoretical inclination, a lot of definitions can be found in the literature. Thus, it is defined as a formal organization because it is established deliberately for the realization of specific goals (Odemigwe 1983). Some see it as a specific type of formal organization, given that a formal organization is a form of a social grouping that is established in a more or less deliberate or purposive manner for the attainment of a special goal (Mouzelis 1975). But our operational definition will be along with Blau's

(1956) “the type of organization designed to accomplish large scale administrative task by systematically coordinating the work of many individuals”.

- ii. Effectiveness: This can generally be looked upon as the extent to which an organization realized its goal and objective. Put in other words, it would mean the capacity to provide or accomplish the correct end. The concern for organizational effectiveness from the total organization level to individual level cases.
- iii. Organization: Is meant any social set up with a structural arrangement in which people are placed to interact to achieve the intended mission, purpose, objectives or goals of the organization as well as the purpose of those who engage in interaction. It is therefore a social institution e.g. universities, churches, government parastatals and other organizations.
- iv. Service: This is a system that provides something that the public needs, organized by public or private sector organizations.
- v. Delivery: The act of taking or giving something to somebody or a group of persons giving assistance, help or service to the public.
- vi. Training Recipient: This means that a person who has returned to or re-entered his/her sponsoring organization after undergoing an external course or training.
- vii. Learning: The effect of experience on subsequent behaviour, (Berelson and Steiner, 1964). Lippitts (1969) definition would be the operational definition. It states that learning implies knowing something one did not have previous knowledge of- this could be a behaviour or a skill.

CHAPTER TWO

This chapter focuses on the literature review and the theoretical framework of the research work.

2.1 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Given a new lease of effectiveness in service delivery to any organization has a continuing concern to organizational scholars. Another way of expressing this statement is to say that the search for organizational effectiveness in service delivery from the total organization is a never-ending exercise.

Environmental dynamics are such that if the concern with effectiveness ceases, organizations would die. To make a meaningful discussion of this section, therefore, it is considered necessary to examine the following:

- A. Classical thoughts on bureaucratic organizations.
- B. Social human relations- a critique of classism.
- C. Post-human relations.
- D. Effect of bureaucracy on the effectiveness of organizations, summarized from the above.

Fredrick W. Taylor (1856-1915) popularly called the “father of scientific management”, profoundly influenced his contemporaries in the field of management and his name became a household name. Taylorism became linked with the study, methods of efficiency and assignment of specific tasks.

He was of the view that the economic interest was the most important to employees, and as a result, a worker would be ready to work with him provided he is very well remunerated. The establishment of standards (which were none existent), was another contribution of his. He sought by using the analytical approach to establish “the standards of performance”, to set-piece rates on an equitable basis. He also concentrated on the best way to do a job and what constituted a fair day’s work. He also introduced the technique of time study.

Henri Fayol (1841-1925) wrote about management from an administrative point of view. He developed a series of principles that aid job management. Fayol felt that all industrial activities could be divided into six groups:

- i. Technical
- ii. Commercial
- iii. Financial
- iv. Security
- v. Accounting
- vi. Managerial

He recognized that as one moves up the organizational hierarchy, the job of the manager becomes less technical and more managerial. From this, he sought to have management processes taught in schools and on the job, in the same capacity as technical activities. He held that management involved forecasting, planning, organizing, coordinating, and controlling. In Fayol's view:

1. **Planning** means examining the future and mapping out an action plan.
2. **Organizing** means building up structures.
3. And **Control** is ensuring that everything conforms with established plans

Lillian Gilbreth (1868-1924) developed the techniques of the motion study. He held that most manual work could be broken down into few simple motions repeated over and over. These primary anagrams and symbols were devised to recording them. He distinguished seventeen elementary groups of movements where all kinds of human activities could be divided. He also investigated the problem of fatigue and its elimination and suggested ways of eliminating needless fatigue.

Morris L. Cooke and Harrington Emerson were among the classical writers on organization and philosophical applications to a wider group of activities. Cooke demonstrated fields, particularly in university operations in city management. Emerson concentrated on introducing improved means to the Santa Fe railroad, and later developed what he termed "the Twelve Principles of Efficiency".

Max Weber (1964) tried to show that there are better ways in which organizational efficiency can be improved. The basic organizational principle underlining his entire work was the principle of increased rationalization of all aspects of human life, thus he sought to show that there is a certain way in which formally free labour can be rationally organized to ensure maximum supply of effort and maximum productivity.

He was led to the conclusion that bureaucracy is by far the most efficiently known method for the performance of complicated tasks of administration and service delivery. His ideal is characterized by the following:

- Specialization hierarchical structured authority
- Systematized rules
- Impersonality
- Secure and Meritocratic career structure

From Max Weber's work, Chinye (1967) collapsed these characteristics into five parts:

- i. Carefully defined positions or offices.
- ii. A hierarchical order with a clear expression of authority and responsibility.
- iii. Selection of personnel on their technical and professional qualifications.
- iv. Rules and regulations governing official actions.
- v. Security of tenure and the possibility of a career by promotion in the hierarchy.

The nucleus of the contribution of these classical writers of bureaucracy is centred on such matters as determining defectives, grouping activities, delegating authority, specifying responsibility and establishing formal relations among employees. It thus plays down behavioural and motivational aspects of an organization and concentrates on formal structural principles. It has been criticized by A.K. Rice (1963), based on a close system with an inherent ability to accommodate changes in the external environment.

Also, C. Meyers (1948), in voicing his reservation against classical bureaucratic writers was of the view that when one considers the whole individual personalities, it is realized that one individual preferred way of working might not be the best way for another. Therefore, imposing a uniform

manner of work does not only damage individuality but causes other socio-psychological disturbances for the employee.

Elton Mayor and his team, after a series of empirical demonstrations on organizational productivity and efficiency, discovered that there is something more important than wages; to him, the work hours, physical capability and other factors and conditions are what often motivates individuals to be effective and productive.

Furthermore, the classical concentration on specialization, the span of control and other elements are rejected as being inconsistent with the needs, wants and commitment required for the provision of quality service.

The social human relations and reactions to the pathologies of classical writers have often been accused of being concerned with making employees happy as though this would inevitably result in high-quality products. To the fact of this, the writers and authorities of this approach were naïve. Blinded by its precise worthy humanitarian service values and its overzealous, it desires to save the individual from the organization, it failed to recognize the problem of conflict and the conflicting interest of the two major parties in industrial relations. And as such, failed to look for the causes as well as the consequences of the causes. Despite the criticism levelled against the school, it gave rise to what is now called post-human relations.

The concept of a socio-technical system is generally credited to E. I. Trist and his associates at the Tavistock Institute in England. According to D. Silverman (1968), the view of an organization as a socio-technical system stresses the interrelationship of technology, environment, the sentiment of the participant and the organizational form or structure. In other words, in studying an organization, rather than being only concerned with the efficiency of methods (or human relations), we must also concern ourselves with the organization's technology vis-à-vis the local environment and the psychology of the people within the organization. It is, therefore, the position of this school that social systems and technical systems must be made harmonious.

The phase of decision theory of bureaucracy brought to the mainstream of organizational thought, an interest in the process of decision-making and the cognitive role of the individual in business enterprises. The beginning of a meaningful analysis of decision theory can better be

traced to Chester I. Bernard, "The functions of the executive" (1938), where he stated that the process of decision-making is a technique for "narrowing ones' choices".

A Simeon outlined three steps involved in decision-making as follows:

- Intelligence activity
- Design activity
- Choice activity

The works of these organizational scholars have contributed immensely to the understanding of bureaucracy, as regards its structure, process and effect. Its dynamic nature shows that it is functional and dysfunctional in actual existence.

Concerning the functional outlook of bureaucracy, WU (1979) has pointed out the importance and necessity of bureaucracy in modern society. He states the bureaucracy has a place in the administrative system for as long as the mechanistic elements continue to hold dominant positions in modern society. While it has extended a strong supporting hand to the bureaucratic system (through strengthening control), it could also be lead to the rise of the organic form of organization in specific areas.

WU maintains that rather than be eliminated, bureaucracy could be developed or transformed into new forms. The survival of modern society is doubtful if there are no pyramidal structures to sustain it. Even adhocracy would not work effectively without a bureaucratic system to coordinate its processes.

The inevitability and need for bureaucracy have also been argued by Lauman, Siegel and Hodge (1970). They pointed that the maintenance of any social system requires the continuous and successful performance of a variety of activities. There is no known system in which every person carries out the same pattern of activities however, there is always the possibility that the features used to distinguish one pattern from another will become distinguishing marks as found in bureaucratic phenomena i.e. authority, status and division of labour.

The certainty of bureaucracy is further demonstrated by Tannenbuam Lauman et al (1974), noting how the absence of property, individual prestige (inside or outside) an organization brings

about the distinction. Also, he pointed out that most specialists and professionals cannot all be grouped on the same organizational level. The very nature of their work (through division of labour and specialization) will not allow the dispensation of bureaucracy.

Mmobuosi and Ekpunobi (1984), also made some valuable contributions in analyzing the nature of bureaucracy. They contended that the existence of these features of bureaucracy as an objective reality does not inhibit the effectiveness of an organization rather, how the people in the organization interpret and evaluate it.

While WU, Tannenbaum, Lauman et al, Mmobuosi and Ekpunobi have appeared to accept some principles of the ideal bureaucracy, R. K. Merton and P. Blau have been the most outstanding critics of Weber and his ideas on bureaucracy.

Merton (1968) in his argument has stated that bureaucratic organizations are dynamic and ever-changing. Although the goals of the individual in the organization might not agree with those of the organization (which might be a cause for concern and in most cases conflict), the rules that have been successfully applied in the past may result in inappropriate responses under different circumstances. This has been the dialectics of bureaucracy.

Here conformity to rules becomes an end in itself, rather than a means to an end. This goal displacement has been what he described as bureaucratic dysfunction. The work of Blau in his analysis of formal and informal structure further classifies the need for informal practices in a formal organization. For him, informal practices could not be divorces from bureaucratic organizations. After conducting a comprehensive study of the behaviour of agents working in one of the nine district agencies of a bureau based in Washington, he discovered that the staff were less interested in taking their problems to their supervisors and that they were more likely to seek each other's assistance for solutions.

From the above analysis, and according to Blau, actual bureaucracy implies the tolerance of informal practices.

Hage and Aiken (1970), Dalton (1950), Wilensky (1967) and other authorities have pointed out the impact of the features of bureaucracy on the adoption of new ideas in organizations.

Firstly, the flow of communication may be inhibited, the existence of many work units and how members perceive the quality of inter-unit relations may be a source of anxiety. These anxieties are likely to occur where work units are interpreted by their leaders and members as constituent spheres of influence. Such transactional issues might not arise, had bureaucracies not been seen to comprise several labour specialized compartments.

Hage and Aiken (1970) associate the extent of organizations readiness for innovativeness with the degree of bureaucratic complexity. Complexity partly arises from the fact of a steady accumulation of knowledge in society. An accumulation that leads to an ever-increasing number of occupations. A paradox however is that a large number of professionals may hamper the flow of ideas in an organization, which could affect the effectiveness of an organization. Blau and Scott (1962) illustrated this in their study of communications in hospitals. They discovered that interactions intended to be more with fellow doctors and nurses with nurses, and if these findings are applied to organizations, the very features of bureaucracy come to mind.

Regarding the factors of centralization as a characteristic of bureaucracy, Hage and Aiken (1970 op.c.t) explain that it could slow down the rate of acceptance and implementation of change. The effect of a high degree of centralization may thus bring into focus the power and authority of politics in the life of organizations. The negative characteristics and effects of bureaucracy have been perceived by some authorities as a challenge to seek alternative organizational machinery in matrix and project teams (Bennis and Slater 1938).

Michels, sees the inevitable division of labour, the vigorously defined hierarchy and rules as leading to less of initiatives, making bureaucracy a mere appendage of the law; with a mania for promotion and prestige. According to Michels, bureaucracy is the sworn enemy of individual liberty and all bold initiatives in matters of internal policy. It is pretty, narrow, rigid and ill-liberal.

The structural nature of bureaucracy together with the principle of impersonality tends to breed depersonalization of social life and infringement on individual sense of autonomy. The net effect is the penchant for disenchantment among certain individuals within hierarchical structures of control.

Max Weber himself recognizes the realities of depersonalization when he observed that:

The more calculability of decision-making and appropriateness for capitalism is fully realized, the more completely it succeeds in achieving the exclusion of love, hatred and every purely personal feeling from the execution of official tasks. In the place of the old-type rules that is moved by sympathy, favour, grace and gratitude, modern culture requires for its sustaining external apparatus, the emotionally detached and hence the rigorously “professional” expert. (In Coser, 1971, p. 23)

Apart from the effect of violation of the individual sense of autonomy and depersonalization, Phillips (1988) to him, hierarchical system of coordination tends to unnecessary bottlenecks and delays that are ultimately counterproductive to prompt and effective execution of tasks and roles.

C. I. Barnard in his view criticized Weber and his ideal type for failing to analyze and compare the correspondence of behaviour in an organization with organizational blueprints. In particular, he failed to account for the fact that in the course of operations, new elements arise in structure which will effectively influence subsequent operations. Such “informal organizations” were considered by Barnard to be necessary to the operation of formal organizations as a means of communication, cohesion and other human relationship elements.

Karl Mannheim in his book “man and society in an age of reconstruction”, pointed to the differences between an organization and its members. This he classified as the substantial and the functional perspectives. The worker is seen as smaller than the organization and relatively inconsequential. Still, without the worker, the organization's goals are unattainable. At the same time, the worker knows a bit of the job that he does in the organization which to Mannheim is the most important thing.

This functional perspective puts the employee in a position of “Blind man and the elephant” where each employee knows only the part of an elephant that he/she touches.

From a substantial perspective, the bureaucracy forces members to conform to the rules which have been drawn up to promote organizational goals. The bureaucrats do not see the number of the organization as a part of the organization.

C. W. Mills, Bagehot and H. Spenser have further contributed to the criticism of bureaucracy. While Mills in his attack was of the view that bureaucracy collapses under routine, Bagehot in his “The English Constitution” warned against the administration of bureaucracy. He did not have a positive outlook on the success of bureaucracy in regulating human society.

H. Spencer in his writing launched an attack on state intervention via bureaucracy in the affairs of society. He was of the position that the more bureaucratic power grows, the less the power of the members of the society and the ability to regulate it.

The Marxian orientation on bureaucracy has been in line with its general perspective of conflict in capitalist society. Marx was greatly concerned with the state of bureaucracy, he conceived the notion that the bourgeoisie capitalist’s society has built within it a bureaucratic mechanism to maintaining class division and class struggle. To Marx, bureaucracy is not an integral part of the social structure, rather, it is meant to protect the interest of the dominant class/ ruling class. Like the state, its main task is to maintain the status quo and the privilege of its master. According to Marx, bureaucracy is only an area of the general process of alienation.

From his radical standpoint, Marx speaks of bureaucratic incompetence as officials lack initiatives and creativity. Specific features of this include what he referred to as ‘sordid materialism’. Recent scholars like Maslow, Herzberg, Mc. Gregor and others have identified the need for friendship, group support, acceptance, approval, recognition, achievement, safety, interpersonal relations and self-actualization as indispensable factors for increased productivity and efficiency in organizations.

The Hawthorne studies (1924-1932) indicated that physiological capabilities alone cannot explain employee behaviour in an organization. As Mouzelis (1985) emphasizes, “Thus, the employee can no longer be perceived as isolated physiological being but as a member of a team or group, whose behaviour is greatly controlled by group norms and values”.

In Joseph La. Palombara (1963) rendition of bureaucracy, he feared that the bureaucracy of a new nation may hamper the growth of a private entrepreneurial class and that where the bureaucracy is cohesive, political parties tend to be passive instrumentalities of administrators.

In another writing of Robert Michels in his book, 'political parties, has shown an intricate fusion of bureaucracy and oligarchy in contemporary society. Michels was mainly concerned with the politics of large scale organizations. He debunked the Marxian notion of organizational bureaucracy in the socialist state as a mere illusion and went further to show that there are some inherent deficiencies in all bureaucratic organisations. He asserted that the oligarchic structure of an organization gave rise to bureaucratic principles, which he called the ruling "elites" that imposes the iron law of oligarchy.

Katz and Kahn (1966) observed that bureaucratic organisations tend to move toward maximization, growth and expansion, and that displacement is a common phenomenon (CF Hall1987).

Ascribing the attribute of Weber's (1947) ideal construct to bureaucracies of the developing areas, most especially the hierarchical arrangement of officers and responsibilities attached to each, some scholars have argued that a bureaucracy where it is not controlled by independent political forces, tend to become self-serving instruments and that policies irrational for a country's economic development but rational in terms of the administrators own self-interest tend to be developed (Rigg, 1966; Lipset1981).

When a political system is dominated by urban elites, Roos and Roos (1971) have shown, bureaucrats, tend to participate in important political decisions, controlling the environment to maximise their influence. This trend becomes manifest given some of the very features of Weber's ideal construct.

While writing about the Burmese bureaucracy, Lucian Pye (1962) had blamed administrative, in that country on three shortcomings: ambivalence over the nature and form of progress. Confusion over the difference between ritual and rationality in administration and an-all pervasive lack of communication- all of which are traced to what Thorstein Veblen has aptly characterized as that of "trained incapacity" in the Burmese cultural values.

Centralization, as a structural arrangement in Weber's ideal construct, is perceived as stifly innovative initiative or causing a delay as ideal pass field or dispersed units toward central authorities who themselves may resent whatever ideas they assess as eroding their power. Besides, original meanings may in the process get distorted people's experiences of central supervisory and competing structures have been amply discussed in Hage and Aiken (1970), Zaltman, et al (1973), Sheriff and Sheriff (1953) and Fernandes (1986).

Similarly, hierarchy, associated with the superior location of a source of reward, also has its negative side as critical and creative subordinates in an organisation may not wish to offend their boss.

Imanyi and Mmobuosi: while writing on bureaucracy were of the view that the quality that organizational members perceive of their work climate affects their mood and mode of performance whether innovative or routine. To them, innovativeness which leads to the effectiveness of an organisation is unlikely where the perceptions are of a culture of rigid rules application, inflexible structures punishment for any form of departure from establishment ways of work, unsupportive and conceivably alimentative and scheming leader as solely transactional rather than transformational leadership which is the main.

It must be stressed in conclusion that though bureaucracy is a functional necessity in an organisation, it must not be an end in itself; rather it should accommodate all other informal activities geared towards the effectiveness of an organisation. Put in other words bureaucracy and informal activities in an organisation should be encouraged rather than being condemned.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The idea that helps explain the dynamic interrelationship of several parts of a large whole as it interacts with its environment has in the last several decades been applied to organizational theory (For example Etzioni, 1964, Katz and Kahn 1966, Lawrence and Lorsch 1967, Kast and Rosenzweig 1970).

As typically defined, a 'system' is thought of as "a set of components surrounded by a boundary which accepts inputs from some other system and discharges outputs into another system (Bernien, 1968 p.111) ". Thus, system theory is concerned with problems of the relationship of structure and of the interdependence rather than the constant attributes of an object (Katz and Kahn, 1966 p.18).

In other words, when we are talking about organisations as a system, we are attending to the combination of parts and elements that form some sort of unique whole. The focus is not on a part as it stands by itself, but rather on how the parts interact with and is related to other parts.

Most, if not all organisation theorists who take an explicit system approach go one step further in their analysis and designate an organisation as an "open system". By the word 'open' in this context is meant the fact that the parts of a system (organisation) do not completely determine the system outputs by themselves, but rather interact with an outside environment that represents situational uncertainty.

Thus, the parts of the organisation system are subject to influence by environment stimuli not directly contained within the system. It must be stressed, however, that a closed system also exists. No doubt, a closed system rarely exists particularly with living components, yet their existence may often be assumed for analytical purposes. To understand a system, it is noteworthy to identify and describe its elements and characteristics. The significant ones include boundaries, 'parts', 'feedback', 'input and output' and 'equilibrium'. The boundary is supposed to tell what a system contains i.e. what may be inside or outside. We may observe the boundary of a system as being physical or tangible, for instance in a plant or assembly line. It may also be abstract or intangible. This applies to a system of role of staff in a small group.

The second element of a system is the parts. These are parts whose inter-relatedness and connectedness leads to the achievement of a given objective or set of objectives. For instance, a University could be said to be a system made of parts like the students, lecturers and the non-academic staff such that if there is a change in one element, it leads to change in the other parts of the system (University).

Feedback may be regarded as a process by which systems receive necessary information as to how well or how badly they are functioning.

It is a self-regulating device. It is expected to feed the information it has gathered back into the system to guide, direct and control its operation e.g., a thermostat that regulated car temperature.

Various forces operate within and upon a system. The system, therefore, tends to achieve a balance called 'equilibrium' (or a steady-state) among these forces which may be in many forms.

In applying system theory to formal organisations, it must be noted that every formal organisation interacts with its environment. This can be clearly illustrated from the fact that it draws its employees (executive and subordinates) from the community; it purchases its supplies and equipment from other firms. Competing firms represent its yardstick for measuring performance. Community resources such as water, electricity and sewage are utilized. "Through wage payments, employee benefit programmes, purchases of goods and services, the business firm affects the welfare of its environment. Similarly, it is affected by and affects the culture of its environment" (Carzo and Yanaizas 1967, p 236).

In the course of interaction, the formal organisation adapts to and plays a part in moulding and shaping its' environment. In effect, therefore, the environment is a "bigger system" (supra system) and has a mutually dependent relation to the formal organisation. No doubt, a formal organisation is aptly depicted as an open system. The real meaning of view an industrial or formal organisation as a system within our thus described framework now requires some scintillating analysis.

Every system has its subsystems. This is true of organisations. The choice of subsystems and the basic unit is a matter of convenience. For our purpose, however, the unit to be viewed as basic to a formal organisation is the individual.

Noteworthy is the observation that subsystems at all levels of a major system have properties and characteristics in common. Each level also has certain unique properties which are a criterion for selecting appropriate levels. Accordingly, we can expect the individual human organism, the face to face workgroup, the functional department, the division and the total organisation to have unique properties as well as properties in common.

System theory does not believe that the behaviour of the whole at any level can be predicted solely by the knowledge of the behaviour of its sub-parts. Conventional organisation theory, however, attempts to predict the behaviour of the organisation based on assumptions about the individual (MC Caregor, 1967 p40).

As was earlier analyzed, a formal organisation as an open system interacts with its large system—the society. Input exists in the form of materials, people, money and economic forces. Product, services and rewards to members, constitute the output. Moreover, an organisation is an organic system, adapting to environmental changes in the system around it.

Lastly, an organisation is a socio-technical system. Not merely being an assembly of building, manpower and money. It consists of the organisation of people and various technologies.

To now relate system theory to the present study, it must be stressed that ASCON operates as a bureaucratic organisation in service delivery. Per bureaucratic tradition, it exemplifies structure such that departments are created interconnected, but each geared towards a specific area and the overall effectiveness of ASCON.

At the operational level, the college's activity focuses on teaching, research and consultancy. Traditionally, courses unit as a subsystem in ASCON often by conversing bring in participants and other facility users. They are the major source of internally generated revenue. All other subsystems i.e. ventures (provide catering, recreational and maintenance services), finance and

supply, library, cooperate affairs and so on complemented these services provided by course units towards the survival and effectiveness of the college ASCON.

Course units as departments, held up by rigid bureaucratic rules associated with bureaucracy as stated by Weber in his ideal construct will cause a state of equilibrium in the entire system. If for instance, the departments in charge of courses fail to bring in participants and other facility users due mainly to the rigid nature of bureaucracy, ventures services would be halted, the library also as a subsystem will not have clients to utilize its services. This would in the long run lead to ineffectiveness in ASCON as a system. On the other hand, improvement in this deficiency stated above in the form of a little flexibility in bureaucratic rules would bring out a positive result in the form of ineffectiveness and a state of equilibrium would be attained due to the modification in the subsystems.

In conclusion, ASCON as a system, to achieve organizational effectiveness in service delivery as a state of equilibrium in the organisation should reduce to some extent some of the bureaucratic features exemplified by Weber in his 'ideal bureaucracy' sine an organisation as a bureaucratic set up has a various department that works as a subsystem towards achieving organizational effectiveness of the system. Any dysfunction in any part can affect others and enhance its effectiveness.

CHAPTER TWO

3.1 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A sample of the population of staff in ASCON will be taken. To do this, the sample random technique will be used to select respondents from the total population. The college is with staff strength of about 347 staff members made of junior and senior members of staff in the college. Of the whole, 120 staff will thus make up the population of the study. To get adequate information from the chosen persons, the questionnaire will be administered, as well as an oral interview. This is because, by its very nature, they are likely to be less expensive than other methods of data collection. They require fewer skills to administer, they can be administered to large and direct individuals simultaneously, and also large respondents have greater confidence in their anonymity (in terms of a questionnaire) and thus are free to express views that they fear might get them into trouble or be disapproved.

While in the aspect of oral interviews, they will enable the researcher to get to know his/her respondent and in the process directly study the respondent in question.

1. The Administrative Staff College of Nigeria (ASCON) is located in Topo – Badagry, Lagos P.M.B 1004 and then a liaison office at the head of the service department, federal secretariat, P.M.B 150, Abuja. ASCON complex at Topo village, Badagry, Lagos is made up of two phases, phase 1 and phase 2.

Phase 1

- Administrative block/department
- The office of director-general
- Maintenance department
- Library/auditorium
- Staff quarters
- Clinic
- Accommodation (1st class)
- Supermarket, shopping mall
- Reservoirs, swimming pool (s), clubhouse etc.

Phase 2

- Staff schools
- Departments
- Computer centres
- Participants hostel blocks

And then the governing board which is the highest policy-making body for the college. At this operational level, the college's activity focuses on the three areas of teaching, research and consultancy which are reconstituted into 3 faculties with departments under the Director-General consists:

A. FACULTY OF GOVERNMENT AND POLICY STUDIES

- i. Human Resource Development Department
- ii. Government and Security Studies Department
- iii. Local Government Department
- iv. Public Administration Management Studies Department

B. FACULTY OF COMPUTER STUDIES AND TECHNOLOGY

- i. Department of computer and information management studies
- ii. Technical and maintenance studies department

C. FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND BUSINESS STUDIES

- i. Economic studies department
- ii. Financial management studies department
- iii. Enterprises management studies department

In addition, the college following a recent reorganization established the following four centres:

- i. Centre for consultancy services
- ii. Centre for distance learning
- iii. Centre for policy research and documentation

Conversely, the following departments in the college offer the following support services:

- i. Administration and welfare (including medical)
- ii. Finance and supplies
- iii. Library
- iv. Maintenance and mechanical

Abuja Campus, Abuja.

The Abuja campus of ASCON has been established at the Lower Usman Danfodio Estate, Abuja F.C.T. The objective for setting up the Abuja campus is to facilitate the extension of the college services to more clients than before, particularly as federal ministries have been moving to Abuja.

At present, the college provides training for public servants in the following areas below. It must also be stated that PGDPA and CPA programmes run for two and five years respectively.

1. The total population of the ASCON employees are made up of about Three Hundred and Forty-Seven (347). While the staff strength of ASCON in the previous years was above a thousand, the staff strength of ASCON dropped drastically, as a result of the retirement of older employees retired and there were little or no incoming members of staff. The staff population of ASCON is categorized according to qualifications and hierarchical order. Below are members of the support staff:

- i. Director General's office
- ii. Administrative department
- iii. Accounts department
- iv. Library department

Staff Hierarchy

Faculty Staff	Junior Research Fellow 11 (JRF11)	Administrative Staff	Assistant Secretary 11
	Junior Research Fellow 1 (JRF1)		Assistant Secretary 1
	Senior Management Development Officer (SMDO)		Senior Assistant Secretary
	Principle Management Development Officer (PMDO)		Principle Assistant Secretary
	Assistant Chief Management Development Officer		Under Secretary
	Chief Management Development Officer		Deputy Secretary
	Assistant Director of Studies		Assistant Director (Admin)
	Director of Studies		Director of Administration

The total population of students in ASCON IN 2007/2008 program summed up to about one thousand, eight hundred and forty. The 2007 programme had more students than the present 2008 which still welcomes incoming participants of the college programme.

3.2 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

In a typical survey/research, the researcher selects a sample of respondents and administers a standardized means of observation, whether by exploratory, descriptive, experimental, research questions (questionnaire), oral interview etc.

Data are collected from the populations for intensive study and analysis. More often than not, the researcher finds out that he/she cannot possibly study all the subjects or items in the population.

Hence the researcher selects a sample from a subset of the total population using any of the above sampling techniques.

Sampling techniques can be purposive or it can be random.

- Sampling techniques are purposive when the sample selected from a subset for the study is being selected for the purpose order to get information on a particular field.
- On the other hand, random sampling techniques are techniques that involve selecting a sample without deciding or thinking in advance about the subjects to be used from the subset.

In this particular survey, the research is done with the use of the questionnaire method and the oral interview method. These two methods of sampling techniques are self-explanatory and do not require further elaborations. The questionnaire and oral interview methods are classified as purposive sampling techniques because the study is focused on a particular organisation. The researchers' questions to the respondents are selected based on the analysis of the activities of the particular organisation or case study at hand.

These two methods of sampling techniques chosen to be used to study the case study are **Primary** forms of data collection. **Primary** methods of data collection are considered principal because there is direct contact between the researcher and respondents.

In this case, the questionnaire and oral interview methods are primary sources of data collection.

1. **Questionnaire Method:** This is a method of collecting data which is done by writing a list of questions that are answered by many people so that information can be collected from the answers and used to carry out a research study. Questionnaires are most directly associated with survey research.

A questionnaire format is as important as the nature and content i.e. questions asked. An improperly laid out questionnaire can get respondents confused and lead respondents to miss questions, and in the extreme may lead them to abandon the questionnaire. Also, the desirability of spreading questions out in the questionnaire cannot be over-emphasized.

2. **Interview Surveys:** This is an alternative method of collecting survey data. Rather than asking respondents to read questionnaires and enter their answers, researchers send interviewers to ask the questions orally and record respondents' answers. Interviewing is typically done in a face to face encounter. One can also undertake a small-scale interview survey yourself.

Studies have shown that respondents seem more reluctant to turndown an interviewer standing on their doorstep than they are to throw away a mail questionnaire. The interviewer can also observe as well as ask questions.

3.3 Methodological Problems.

As sociologists, we have several problems associated with our research work despite our use of scientific methods. The problems and limitations of sociological scientific methodology originate from the fact that sociology cannot be a natural science but a social science dealing with human beings and their society. People are so different and cannot be treated the same way as natural objects. Their behaviour is prone to change under observation and/or experimentation.

According to Percy Cahon (1958), social behaviour cannot be seen as casually regular behaviour, hence, a change or variation in their behaviour is inevitable.

In my own research study/ methodology, I was faced with several problems:

- There were difficulties in drafting the questions for my questionnaire; the question had to be based on the case study (ASCON) in particular.
- It was not easy moving around, trying to motivate and enlighten the members of the organisation to fill the questionnaire.
- Some people were outrightly rude and uneasy to converse with.
- There were several disagreements during the focus group discussion.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Research findings are incomplete until it has been tested. To validate or invalidate the stated hypothesis, simple percentages and chi-square as a measure of association between two or more variables were used. As stated in the methodology, 120 questionnaires were distributed and only 112 were returned after being filled.

To properly understand our population of the study, I would begin with a sample of a few characteristics of respondents' as examined.

Table 2: The Sex Distribution of Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	91	81.2
Female	21	18.8
Total	112	100

Source: Field Data August, 2008.

This table shows that male respondents constitute 81.2% and female respondents 18.8% of the total distribution. In raw figures, our sample is made up of 91 males and 21 females in the organisation. This implies that more males than females responded to the questionnaire.

Table 3: The Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
0 -17	0	0.0
18 -35	35	31.2
36 -53	40	35.7
54 – 71	32	28.6
71 and above	5	4.5
TOTAL	112	100

Source: *Field Data August 2008.*

This table of the age distribution of the respondents shows 0.0% of ages between 0 -17 years, 31.3% between 18 -35, 35.7% between the ages of 36 -53, 28.6% between 54 – 71 and 4.5% between the ages of 71 and above. It, therefore, implies that most of the respondents are between the ages of 36 and 53, while the least age group/distribution of respondents are between 0-71 years of age which produced a 0.0%.

Table 4: The Marital Status Distribution of Respondents

Status	Frequency	Percentage %
Single	28	25.0
Married	75	66.9
Separated	7	6.3
Divorced	2	1.8
Total	112	100

Source: *Field Data August, 2008.*

The table above is based on the marital status of respondents' and shows that singles make up 25.0% of the distribution, married people make up 66.9%, those who are separated make up 6.3% and the divorced make up 1.8%. This implies a higher per cent of married people in the distribution of those who responded to the questionnaire, followed by the singles, then they separated, leaving only about 2 divorced respondents.

Table 5: The Educational Attainment Distribution of Respondents

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage %
Nursery/Primary	9	8.1
Secondary/Tech/College	17	15.2
A.T.C/Polytechnic/College of Agriculture	11	9.8
University	53	47.3
Senior Executive Course	22	19.6
Total	112	

Source: *Field Data August 2008.*

This table shows that respondents with the educational attainment of nursery and primary level are 8% those with secondary and/or technical college attainment are 15.2% those with A.T.C and/or polytechnic, college of Agriculture/Education is 9.8% of the distribution, those with a university degree attainment are 47.3% and finally those with senior Executive courses attainment are 19.6%. Thus, this shows that there are respondents with university attainment than any other educational attainment, followed by those with the senior executive courses and so on according to their percentage.

Table 6: The Occupation Distribution of Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage %
Clerks	31	27.7
Administrative officer	42	37.5
Civil Servant	28	25.0
Self Employed	6	5.3
Diplomat	5	4.5
Total	112	100

Source: *Field Data August, 2008.*

The table above shows that more administrative officers responded to the questionnaire with 37.5% followed by the clerks with 27.7% then the civil servants with 25.0%, self-employed staff with 5.4% and the few diplomats with 4.5%. Thus, this means that most respondents are administrative officers and the least respondents are diplomats.

Table 7: The Income Distribution of Respondents

Income Rates	Frequency	Percentage %
7,500 – 10,000	6	5.4
10,500 – 13,000	18	16.1
13,500 – 16,000	9	8.0
16,500 – 19,000	13	11.6
19,500 And Above	66	58.9
Total	112	100

Source: *Field Data August, 2008.*

The table above shows more respondents are being paid income of 19,500 and above followed by those paid between 10,500 and 13,000, than those paid between 16,500 and 19,000, than those paid between 13,500 and 16,000, the least number of respondents are those who are paid between 7,500 and 10,000 with 5.4%.

This then implies that most of the people that responded to the questionnaire are under the income rate of 19,500 and above with 58.9% (66 in number).

Table 8: The Religion Distribution of Respondents

Religion	Frequency	Percentage %
Christian	69	61.9
Muslim	43	38.4
Atheism	0	0.0
Total	112	100

Source: *Field Data August, 2008.*

The table shows that the percentages of Christians are more in the distribution of respondents, they make up 61.6% with 69 in the frequency. While the Muslims make up 38.4%, 43 in number and atheists do not exist in the distribution of respondents.

Table 9: The Residence Distribution of Respondents

Residence	Frequency	Percentage %
Urban	56	50.0
Sub - Urban	35	14.3
Semi -Urban	16	31.2
Rural	5	4.5
Total	112	100

Source: *Field Data August, 2008*

The table above shows the percentages of respondents that reside in various areas as outlined above. From the respondents, urban dwellers are in majority with 50.0% followed by the sub-urban dwellers with 14.3%, then the semi-urban dwellers and finally the rural dwellers with 4.5% only.

In conclusion, there was a very little number of respondents from rural areas with just 5 in number.

Table 10: The Rank Distribution of Respondents.

Rank	Frequency	Percentage %
Clerical Officer	57	50.8
Junior Officer	20	17.9
Admin. Officer 1	15	13.4
Admin. Officer 11	15	13.4
Senior Officer	5	4.5
Total	112	100

Source: *Field Data August, 2008.*

The table above shows that there are 50.0% of clerical officers in ASCON, 17.9% of junior officers, 13.4% of administrative officers 11 and only 4.5% of senior officers. Which mean more clerical officers, and the least number of respondents of senior officers?

CROSS-TABULATION OF VARIABLES AND IMPORTANCE OF BUREAUCRACY IN ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS.

Table 10: Sex and Bureaucracy as a means of achieving organizational effectiveness.

Sex	High	Average	Low	Others	Total
Male	81 (72.3)	7 (5.6)	2 (1.8)	1 (0.9)	91 (81.3)
Female	10 (8.9)	6 (5.4)	1 (0.9)	4 (3.6)	21 (18.7)
Total	91 (81.3)	13 (11.6)	3 (2.7)	5 (4.5)	112 (100)

This table shows that a majority of the male respondents to the questionnaire believe that bureaucracy is highly a means of achieving organizational effectiveness. And only 1 person thinks otherwise. As for the females, 10 females out of 21 believe that bureaucracy is highly a means of achieving organizational effectiveness.

Which means to most ASCON staff bureaucratic tradition in ASCON as a means of achieving organizational effectiveness is high? Yes.

Table 11: Age and Bureaucracy as a means of achieving organizational effectiveness

Age	High	Average	Low	Others	Total
0.17	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
18 -35	21 (18.7)	6 (5.4)	2 (1.8)	6 (5.4)	35 (31.3)
36 -53	28 (25.0)	3 (2.7)	4 (3.6)	5 (4.5)	40 (35.7)
54 -71	12 (10.7)	15 (13.4)	1 (0.9)	4 (3.6)	32 (28.5)
71 & Above	3 (2.7)	2 (1.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (4.5)
Total	64 (57.1)	26 (23.2)	7 (5.6)	15 (13.4)	112 (100)

In this table, respondents between the ages of 36 - 53 are of the strong opinion that bureaucracy is highly a means of achieving effectiveness in organisations with 28 responds with 35.7 % of this opinion.

Table 12: Educational Attainment and Bureaucracy as a means of achievement of organizational goals

Educational Attainment	High	Average	Low	Others	Total
Nursery/Primary	3 (2.7)	5 (4.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.9)	9 (8.0)
Secondary/Tech/College	9 (8.0)	6 (5.4)	1 (0.9)	1 (0.9)	17 (15.2)
A.Tc/Polytechnic./College .of Agric.	5 (4.5)	2 (1.8)	2 (1.8)	2 (1.8)	11 (9.8)
University	30 (26.8)	13 (11.6)	7 (5.6)	3 (2.7)	53 (47.3)
Senior Executive Courses	14 (12.5)	4 (3.6)	1 (0.6)	3 (2.7)	22 (19.6)
Total	61 (54.5)	30 (26.9)	11 (9.8)	10 (8.9)	112 (100)

The table above shows that at most levels of educational attainment of the respondents, the majority of them are of the high opinion that bureaucracy is a means of achieving organizational effectiveness. A few are of the average opinion, a few others are of the low opinion and the remaining had their personal opinions to contribute.

We had a total of 61 under the high column and a total of 11 under the low column.

Table 13: Marital Status and Bureaucracy as A Means of Achieving Organizational Goals.

Marital Status	High	Average	Low	Others	Total
Single	15 (13.4)	6 (5.4)	2 (1.8)	5 (4.5)	28 (25.0)
Married	55 (46.1)	12 (10.7)	2 (1.8)	6 (5.4)	75 (66.9)
Separated	4 (3.6)	2 (1.8)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.9)	7 (6.3)
Divorced	2 (1.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.8)
Total	76 (67.5)	20 (17.8)	4 (3.6)	12 (10.7)	112 (100)

The table above has proved that 15 respondents of the singles that responded to the questionnaire agreed that bureaucracy is a means of achieving organizational goals. But with 55%

are of the view that bureaucracy is a means of achieving organizational goals, married people seem to have overshadowed all the others in the chart.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING AND INTERPRETATION

Table 14: Relationship Between Strict Adherence to Bureaucratic Rules and Staff Initiatives.

Strict Adherence To Bureaucratic Rules	Employee Initiatives		Row Total
	Allowed	Not	
Allowed	67 (59.8)	18 (16.1)	85 (75.8)
Not Allowed	15 (13.4)	12 (10.7)	27 (24.1)
Column Total	82 (73.2)	30 (26.8)	112 (100)

Source: Field survey August, 2008

Null Hypothesis (Ho) – There is no relationship between strict adherence to bureaucratic rules and worker’s initiatives in ASCON, Lagos.

Alternative Hypothesis (Hi) – There is a relationship between strict adherence to bureaucratic rules and worker’s initiatives in ASCON, Lagos.

To statistically test this hypothesis, responses gotten from questions 18 and 19 were cross-tabulated above.

Using the chi-square statistical tabular formulae,

$\sum (o - e)^2$ where o = observed value

E e = expected value derived from the served

Σ = sum

To find the expected value = $\frac{\text{column total} \times \text{row total}}$

Total no of respondents

Expected for cell a = $\frac{85 \times 82}{112} = 62.2$

112

Expected for cell b = $\frac{85 \times 30}{112} = 22.8$

112

Expected for cell c = $\frac{27 \times 82}{112} = 19.8$

112

Expected for cell d = $\frac{27 \times 30}{112} = 7.2$

112

Cell	O	E	o-e	(o-e) ²	$\frac{(o-e)^2}{E}$
A	67	62.2	4.8	23.04	0.37
B	18	22.8	- 4.8	23.04	1.01
C	15	19.8	- 4.8	23.04	1.16
D	12	7.2	4.8	23.04	3.2
					5.74

Calculate chi-square (χ^2) = 5.74

To find tabular chi -square (χ^2) values

Df = (c-1) (r -1) where c = total no of column = 2

r = total no of row = 2

df = (2 -1) (2 -1)

= 1x1

=1

At 0.05 level of significance, under df = 1

Table chi-square (χ^2) value =10.7

X² value = 10.7

Decision Rule

Since tabular value 10.7 is less than the calculated value of 16.94, “bureaucracy is positively related to organizational effectiveness”. Based on the data collected from the questionnaires administered during the survey in which 56 respondents agreed on this while the remaining were on the contrary of this opinion/view.

Given the foregoing facts, I may conclude that bureaucracy is positively related to organizational effectiveness.

My findings are in support of the view of R. K. Merton (1968) and Bennis and Slater (1938) who were of the view that the negative characteristics and effects of bureaucracy have been perceived as a challenge to seek alternative organisations machinery in matrix and project teams.

In carrying out this research study, I made use of about three methods of data collection to get adequate information from respondents based on ASCON concerning its bureaucratic and organizational effectiveness in service delivery.

As mentioned above, the three methods used in research methodology on this research work are as followed.

- Questionnaire methods
- Oral interview method
- Focus group discussion

Simultaneously, the three methods were administered and I got equivalent responses from all three methods, although a few of the questions were interrelated.

The questionnaires were administered to all the available members of the staff ASCON and possible responses were got with 112 respondents.

The oral interview questions were answered and provided by;

Mr. AA Rabi, B.Sc. (Hons) ABU, MPA, Lagos.

Director of Administration.

While the Focus Group Discussion Guide was provided by a group of selected few from the staff of ASCON. Everyone's opinion in this discussion is of great importance.

The questionnaire responses were used in working on the hypothesis statement and other charts.

While the oral interview responses were equivalent and corresponded with that of the response of the questionnaire, as well as the Focus Group Guide Discussion.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The following findings were made in the course of the research.

1. The socio-economic characteristics of respondents show that married staff are in the majority and are in the age range of 36-53 years old. Employees were found to possess diverse qualifications and this has placed them in their area of specialization. It must be stressed in passing also, that a great deal of the senior officer Cadre from the bulk of the senior staff in this organisation. This is in connection with the policy of the establishment which focuses on a university degree or other higher educational qualification: due to the sensitive nature of its programmes.
2. Table 14 proved the hypothesis right, it means strict and rigid rules application informal organisation is often detrimental to the organisation since it stifles employees' initiative and innovative drive.
3. Table 14 observed that the need for revitalizing an organisation is no doubt a functional necessity. It must be stated, however, that the factors in Weber's bureaucracy do not mechanistically create the need for effectiveness. This is because it is extremely difficult to find in a bureaucratic organisation where officials do not exhibit sentiments in the conduct of official tasks. This is because of the various socio-cultural characteristics of the organisation staff.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It must be stated at this stage that understanding organizational behaviour is a 'must' for organizational staff, especially on the higher level of incumbents. For organizational effectiveness, the principles of ideal bureaucracy outlined by Weber should first be assessed by managers and employees and the relevant ones to the effectiveness of their organisation.

Also, bureaucracy as a concept should be subjected to modification and structure to enhance organizational productivity and continuity.

IMPLICATION OF STUDY

Like the researcher pointed out in chapters one and two of this work, most especially when reviewing relevant literature to this study, it was noted that there was a great deal of work done in this area of study. Consequently, the major contribution of this research study is that it will serve as literature in this area of study.

Secondly, the wide conception in several academic quarters regarding the role of bureaucracy is brought to the book in this work. Since it is an investigation aimed at testing the role of bureaucracy and organisation effectiveness, it points at the dysfunctional nature of bureaucracy which would allow the government to develop a form of bureaucracy that would help promote national development as against sticking to the ideal principles of Weber.

Finally, organizational reality must comprehend not only the bureaucrats, administrators, managers and the military officer but equally to employees and employers in an organisation and the society in general.

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APPENDIX 1

UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIOLOGY

ABUJA.

QUESTIONNAIRE

Sir/Madam,

This study is being undertaken in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the undergraduate study in the Department of Sociology, University of Abuja, FCT. Abuja. This questionnaire aims at studying Bureaucracy and Organizational Effectiveness. A case study of Administrative Staff College of Nigeria, Topo-Badagry.

The questions below are designed to help me in my research. Any information given here will be treated as confidential.

QUESTIONNAIRE

Please tick (/) or fill the gaps as appropriate.

Sex: Male [] Female []

Age:	0-17 [] 18-35 [] 36-53 [] 54-71 [] 72 and above []
Marital Status:	Single [] Married [] Divorced [] Separated []
Educational Attainment	Nursery/Primary [] Secondary/Technical college [] A.T.C/ Polytechnic/ College of Agric. [] University [] Senior Executive Course [] University [] Senior Executive Courses []
What is your occupation	
Annual income	
Religion	
Residence	
Status	

SECTION B

ORGANIZATION DATA

1. How long have you worked in ASCON?	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
2. What would you attribute to the success of ASCON?	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
3. What do you think are its problems/failure	<hr/> <hr/> <hr/>
4. How often does ASCON management fail to conform to the organizational goal?	Often () very often () rarely () often () not applicable () Indicate others ()
5. Do you think ASCON'S organization effectiveness can be achieved through cooperation by its staff management?	Yes () no applicable () Indicate others ()
6. How do you rate bureaucratic tradition in ASCON as a means of	

achieving organizational effectiveness?	High () low () Indicate others ()
7. Every organisation has a set of formalized ways of regulating its members. Do you think this could apply to ASCON?	Yes () No ()
If not, why?	
Does strict adherence to organizational rules allow you as ASCON staff to use your initiative?	Yes () No () Not () applicable () Indicate others ()
Are you allowed sometimes to use your initiative outside the established rules of ACON and civil service procedure?	Allowed () Not allowed () Not applicable () Indicate others ()
Bureaucracy is regarded to be slow to change, innovation and reform. Does this apply to ASCON?	Yes () No () Not applicable () Indicate other ()
If 'yes' would you agree that it could affect ASCON'S effectiveness in the training of students and awards of certificates?	Yes () No applicable () Indicates other ()
Does supervision of ASCON by the head of service bring about effectiveness in the organization?	Yes () No ()
In your opinion/view, what do you think should be done to improve the performance of ASCON as a training institution	 <hr/> <hr/>